

 GLOMICAVE

D1.3 Knowledge graph construction using integration plug-ins for automated collection

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Executive summary

Data mining and semantic modelling strategies are needed to create the GLOMICAVE's knowledge base, containing omics data extracted from referent data repositories. This deliverable describes the methodological approach for building the knowledge graph and also, the applied techniques to build it inside the GLOMICAVE digital architecture. More specifically, this document presents the construction of the GLOMICAVE knowledge graph through the adaptation and extension of a pre-existing semantic data model called ISA¹ (Investigation, Study, Assay) to the adoption of other standards and enable data harmonization between omics information. The elaborated approach and semantic model (ontology) is publicly available in the following URL:

<https://w3id.org/def/isa-glomicaive/>

The design and implementation of the GLOMICAVE semantic model add significant value to:

- Support the data representation to enable homogenization between data sources and increase the knowledge base.
- Provide metadata and context-based information to interlink scientific outputs, in that case related to multi-omics repositories.
- Generating open linked data related to omics experiments.
- Support the elaboration of complementary data analysis.

To collect all this information a set of plug-ins (one per repository) has been developed to gather data on demand. From the data collected in raw format, a transformation to include context-based information (semantic metadata) is performed based on the concepts and terms defined under the extended ontology. To enable a data understanding, the present deliverable also includes a dashboarding tools to interact with the data and validate the correct data gathering from the repositories considering the omics experiments.

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¹ <https://isa-specs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/isamodel.html>

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List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
EC	European Commission
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
EU	European Union
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GEO	Gene Expression Omnibus
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
ISA	Investigation, Study, Assay
JSON	Javascript Object Notation
JSON-LD	Javascript Object Notation Linking Data
OWL	Ontology Web Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SOFT	Simple Omnibus Format in Text
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SQL	Structured Query Language
TSV	Tab-Separated Values
TTL	Terse RDF Triple Language
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1. Introduction

The overarching objective of WP1 is the data mining of public repositories for constructing the GLOMICAVE's knowledge-base (technically referred to as knowledge graph). In short, this knowledge graph contains quantitative and qualitative data from omics data repositories, and will be used by WP4, to discover new relationships and patterns by the use of machine learning algorithms and techniques.

In that sense, this document is mainly focused on the description of the semantic model (ontology) of GLOMICAVE as part of the process for the knowledge graph construction. The process of data acquisition from the different repositories were described in Task 1.1 and the selection of potential ontologies to representation this data were reported and selected under Task 1.2. Complementary to this work performed, the knowledge graph has been built under the Task 1.3 considering previous insights. The methodological procedure to build this knowledge graph can be summarised in the following phases: (1) data acquisition from the repositories; (2) extension and construction of the GLOMICAVE ontology based on ISA model; and (3) mappings and construction of the knowledge graph based on the information stored in the relational data base.

Furthermore, this steps cover the representation of the data acquired from public repositories and the subsequent transformation of this data to include semantic metadata. This transformations and final construction of the knowledge graph served to improve data understanding and provenance. Subsequently, the construction of the knowledge graph facilitate to harmonise data thanks to agree on a common terminology and context information. Thus, the GLOMICAVE ontology catalogue the entities involved to define experimental meta-data and its relationships. The elaborated ontology can be accessed through the following URL:

<https://aolite.github.io/isa-glomicave/OnToology/isa-glomicave.ttl/documentation/doc/index-en.html>

The GLOMICAVE ontology will be one of the main elements to represent the information and the subsequent context (meta-data). The proposed ontology will support the research in the complex interactions within molecules and omic layers, also facilitate the integration of scientific literature and experimental data in future work packages.

The resultant data lake (Zhao, 2019) will be the base for data analytics in the development of future WPs' (WP2, WP3, WP4), visualization (WP5) and elaboration of services and research in different demo-cases (WP6).

The work described in this document is based in the previous tasks: "1.1.-Selection and integration of source omic data repositories" and "1.2-Common data model for harmonising omic data". In detail, this task (1.3) is aimed to retrieve the data from repositories from task 1.1 and represent it through the data model from task 1.2.

1.1 Objectives

Task 1.3 is in the scope of the WP1, which the primary focus is to integrate and harmonise the different omic datasets into a digital structure (data lake). This digital structure will permit the sharing and exploration of the information using common data exchange format based on standards (JSON-LD, RDF/XML, TTL, etc). The objectives of task 1.3 are to (i) develop different plug-ins to access and retrieve the data of the repositories identified in task 1.1; (ii) develop and expend ISA model to the definition of a common semantic framework of terms and interlink between terms; and (iii) construction of the knowledge graph to be included into the GLOMICAVE architecture.

1.2 Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- **Section 2** describes the main concepts and definitions to be able to follow and understand what is portrayed in the deliverable.
- **Section 3** is focused on explaining the repositories selected and the data understanding of the collected information.
- **Section 4** describes the ontology construction based on the [SAMOD methodology](#).
 - o **Section 4.1** ontology in the scope of GLOMICAVE project.
 - o **Section 4.2** language of implementation to represent the ontology.
 - o **Section 4.3** meta-data model (ISA) and mapping with repositories.
 - o **Section 4.4** ontology presentation and description.
 - o **Section 4.5** ontology documentation and publication.
- **Section 5** Methodological approach to build the GLOMICAVE Knowledge graph.
- **Section 6** Description of the main conclusions and future work.

2. Main concepts and definitions

As baseline to introduce the work done in Task 1.3, it is important to clarify the concepts used to achieve the objectives of this task, as well as a brief description of the technologies involved:

- **Knowledge graph:** Knowledge graph is also known as semantic network, which represents a network of real-world entities -i.e., objects, situations, or concepts- and illustrates the relationships between them. This information is usually stored in graph database and visualized as a graph structure ² (Wöß, September 2016).
- **Metadata:** is defined as the data providing information about one or more aspects of the data. Basically, is data describing data in terms of type, structures and syntax, and the most common languages are RDF, XML and HTML.
- **Data Model:** is a representation of a system. It consists of concepts used to help people know, understand, or simulate a subject the model represents. It's a set of concepts representing objects and their relationships in a particular application domain. Also determines the structure of data represented in a graphical form.
- **Ontology:** An ontology is a formal explicit description of concepts in a domain of concepts and properties of each concept describing various features and attributes of the concept and restrictions. An ontology together with a set of individual instances of classes constitutes a knowledge base. There is a fine line where the ontology ends, and the knowledge base begins.³
- **JSON-LD:** is a lightweight Linked Data format. Its is easy for humans to read and write structured data using open vocabularies like [schema.org](#). It is based on the already successful JSON format and provides a way to help JSON data interoperable at web-scale providing search-engines with contextual information using semantic technologies.⁴⁵
- **Python:** interpreted, object-oriented, high level programming language with dynamic semantics. Is simple and easy to learn syntax emphasizes readability and therefore reduce the cost of program maintenance.⁶
- **SPARQL:** is an RDF query language, or a semantic query language for databases, able to retrieve and manipulate data stored in RDF format.

² shorturl.at/InCJP

³ <http://www.ksl.stanford.edu/people/dlm/papers/ontology-tutorial-noy-mcguinness.pdf>

⁴ <https://json-ld.org/>

⁵ <https://wordlift.io/blog/en/entity/json-ld/>

⁶ <https://www.python.org/doc/essays/blurb/>

- **Amazon Athena:** Amazon Athena is an interactive query service that makes it easy to analyse data directly in Amazon Simple Storage Service (Amazon S3) using standard SQL. With a few actions in the AWS Management Console, you can point Athena to data stored in Amazon S3 and start using standard SQL to execute ad hoc queries and return results in seconds.
- **RDF (Resource Description Framework):** is a standard for data interchange that is used for representing highly interconnected data. Each RDF statement is a three-part structure consisting of resources where every resource is identified by a URI. Representing data in RDF allows information to be easily identified, disambiguated, and interconnected by AI systems.⁷
- **Amazon Neptune:** is a representation of a system. It consists of concepts used to help people know, understand, or simulate a subject the model represents. It's a set of concepts representing objects and their relationships in a particular application domain. Also determines the structure of data represented in a graphical form.

3. Repositories selected and data obtained

A total of four repositories were selected covering both genomics and metabolomics data. Proteomics repositories were excluded due to the limited number of annotated data available, and the technical challenges of processing proteomics raw data. The repositories selected included repositories containing quantitative data (annotated data), such as Metabolights, ArrayExpress and GEO, and raw data, such as ENA. This deliverable covers the data mining approach for retrieving quantitative data and raw data from the public repositories and the deposition of the quantitative data in the knowledge graph. The processing of the raw data is described in the deliverable D1.4 (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Overarching goal of the deliverable (in red).

3.1 Plug-ins

During the development of the task, a set of plugins were developed to enable repository querying and data conversion from the different sources and its future integration into the knowledge graph. These plug-ins access the information using specific data exchange mechanisms specifically coded for acquiring data from each repository. The objectives of this plug-ins are: retrieve the data, store the data in a structured database, and convert this data to be integrated in the knowledge graph.

The plug-ins were build using **Python** programming language, since it's one of the four languages (Python, R, Julia, and Scada) supported by **Jupyter Notebook**, which is a web-based interactive environment for creating notebook documents. A notebook document basically is a browser-based computer programming environment that takes single user inputs and executes them and returns the results to the user. This notebook can contain code, text, mathematics, plots and rich media.

⁷ <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

The data is initially stored in structured SQL database “S3 Buckets” inside AWS architecture to maintain the provenance of the information. Then, with the objective of construct a knowledge graph is necessary to instantiate the GLOMICAVE ontology with the data retrieved using the terms and relations defined in the ontology specifications, that follows the terms of the ISA model. Lately, this information is stored in the graph database **Amazon Neptune**, and will allow to query this data and construct the graph through the semantic query language **SPARQL**.

3.2 Dashboard

As part of the process for the data acquisition it has been developed a simple dashboard, in order to have quick view of which data are getting and easily validate it. Since it's been required an expert on the domain, this dashboard allow to the developer and the expert a better understanding which data could be useful for the project. Moreover, this dashboard is a valuable tool to test data conversion process and validation.

Figure 2 Dashboard structure

- **Tabs division:** As is shown in
- Figure 2, this dashboard is divided by tabs. Each tab presents the data of the molecules represented in the table.
- **Filter:** This dashboard allows to filter the data to not obtain large amounts of data and improve the user experience. In the case of
- Figure 2, is filtering by the key entity “Study”. As is shown in the
- Figure 2, permits to select the study id from the pre-loaded list or just writing it.

Select study ✕ ▼

Export table to csv All metabolites to csv

Data export

Study ID	DataBase ID	Chemical Formula	Smiles	Inchi
MTBLS321	CHEBI:78320	C3H6O3	CC(O)C(O)=O	InChI=1S/C3H6O... 2(4)3(5)6/h2,4H,1... (H,5,6)

Figure 3 Dashboard data table data export

Metabolite ID	Taxid	Species	Concentrations
Lactic acid (2TMS)	NCBITAXON:http...	Homo sapiens	
Hexanoic acid (1TMS)	NCBITAXON:http...	Homo sapiens	

Concentrations

Figure 4 Dashboard data table concentrations

Once selected the study, the user is able to query the collected data from the repository and process only the most useful information for the project. When data is loaded in the table, user is also able to:

- Data export:** There are two buttons available to export data in the example of Figure 3, “Export table” and “All metabolites”. In the case of the repository of “Metabolights”, since does not contain a large amount of data we consider as a feasible option to export to CSV (comma-separated values) all repository, and that’s what the dashboard do when user selects the option “All metabolites to CSV”. In the case of “Export table to CSV” the dashboard only exports the data represented in the table. In both cases, the information exported is represented in the following CSV structure:

[Study, Total amount of metabolites, Species, [File name 1, File name 2, File name ...n]]

 - File names:** Each study could contain more than one TSV (tab-separated values) file (in case of metabolights), in that case, the last part of the csv row is listed all the file names where the data is obtained.
 - Total amount:** is the sum of all rows of all the files.
- Concentration’s view:** This button shows the concentrations and its values associated to each sample (Figure 4). When the button is clicked a pop-up window is open with the concentrations table, like shown in next Figure 5.

Study ID	DataBase ID	Chemical Formula	Smiles	Inchi	Metabolite ID	Taxid	Species	Concentrations
MTBLS321	CON_BASA_567795	CON_BASA_574488	CON_BASA_580552	CON_BASA_581904	CON_BASA_587625			
MTBLS321	2097723	2818043	1861952	4505129	3544817			

Figure 5 Dashboard concentrations visualization

3.3 Repositories

3.3.1 Metabolites

The repository selected for data acquisition of Metabolites is **Metabolights**.

Metabolights repository provides an API REST⁸ with a set of end points to access the data. Data is provided in JSON format. The relevant data for GLOMICAVE is found in the “tsv” (tab-separated values) files. From all the data of that files we have selected the more relevant for GLOMICAVE, which are:

- **Study:** is the name of the study and its id code
- **Study title:** The study name. It allows providing the title of the study to the users in the GLOMICAVE platform graphical interface when, using WP4, a relationship is found for a particular metabolite of this study.
- **Sets of concentrations of each assay:** each TSV file from the study contains a list of assays, each assay contains a list of concentrations identified by id and its value. Specifically, the values are:
 - **Database identifier:** This is a unique identifier for the observed metabolite name. It will allow unequivocal identification of the metabolite which concentration is being reported.
 - **Chemical formula:** The metabolite chemical formula.
 - **Smiles:** Smiles allows retrieving structural information of the metabolite, also enabling computational structural comparison with other metabolites (i.e., finding other metabolites with a similar molecular structure).
 - **Inchi:** an alternative to SMILES. Differences between Smiles and Inchi are outside the scope of this deliverable.
 - **Metabolite identification:** (i.e., metabolite name). The metabolite name will be used in cases where the database identifier/smiles or inchi are not specified.
 - **Taxid:** The taxonomical identification of the organism from which the data has been acquired.
 - **Species:** Indicates the name of the organism from which the data has been acquired.
 - **Concentration values:** Relative or absolute concentration values in samples.

⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/ws/api/spec.html>

3.3.2 Genomics

GEO (Gene Expression Omnibus) repository provides access to its data through FTP protocol⁹. This repository exposes its data in files of “SOFT” type format structure.

- **Name:** The study unique identifier. The identifier allows tracing the data to its original study, in turn ensuring traceability to e.g., retrieve additional metadata in the future.
- **Title:** the study name. It allows providing the title of the study to the users in the GLOMICAVE platform graphical interface when, using WP4, a relationship is found for a particular gene of this study.
- **Description:** a short study description. It serves the same function as the title (see above).
- **Type:** short (standardized) description of the technology used (e.g., array, next-gen seq, etc).
- **Pubmedid:** Pubmed’s identifier of the scientific paper reporting the use of this dataset (original publication).
- **Platform:** an identifier of the genomics technology used.
- **Platform organism:** the organism used for the platform identifier.
- **Platform technology:** a short and standardized description of the technology used.
- **Sample type:** genomic entity type (RNA, DNA, etc).
- **Expression file:** the quantitative data.
 - *Gene id:* contains the ID for each gene.
 - *Expression data:* Expression values in samples.

Array Express¹⁰:

- **Title/name:** the study name. It allows providing the title of the study to the users in the GLOMICAVE platform graphical interface when, using WP4, a relationship is found for a particular gene of this study.
- **Description:** a short study description. It serves the same function as the title (see above).
- **Organism:** Indicates the name of the organism from which the data has been acquired.
- **Array:** An identifier of the genomics technology used.
- **Experiment type:** a short and standardized (via keywords) description of the technology used.
- **Expression file:** the quantitative data.
 - *Gene id:* contains the ID for each gene of the specific organism as described in the corresponding Genome Assembly and Annotation report of the organism.
 - *Expression data:* Expression values in samples.

ENA. European Nucleotide Archive¹¹:

- **Experiment Accession:** The study unique identifier. The identifier allows tracing the data to its original study, in turn ensuring traceability to e.g., retrieve additional metadata in the future.
- **Title:** the study name. It allows providing the title of the study to the users in the GLOMICAVE platform graphical interface when, using WP4, a relationship is found for a particular gene of this study.
- **Organism:** Indicates the name of the organism from which the data has been acquired.
- **Library Strategy:** Type of omics technology. This is needed for data annotation.
- **Library Source:** Type of omics technology. This is needed for data annotation.
- **Library Name:** This is needed for data annotation.

⁹ <https://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/datasets/>

¹⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress/>

¹¹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

- **Raw data:** all the corresponding RAW data files will be downloaded and prepared for annotation via what is described in the Deliverable 1.4.

4. Ontology development

4.1 Scope

The main scope of the GLOMICAVE T1.3 ontology is to represent many types of information:

- (i) Context-based information about the experimental metadata (i.e., sample characteristics, technology and measurement types, sample-to-data relationships) so that the resulting data and discoveries are reproducible and reusable; and
- (ii) Represent the information from multiple omic repositories that are storing a heterogeneous number of omics datasets

These variables and information will conform the semantic modelling and contextualization of the different experiments from the selected repositories, based on the definition of investigations, studies and assays.

So, one of the main aspects of the ontology is to make understandable the information collected from the different repositories and harmonize such information under a common data model (ISA data model ¹²). Based on this, the ontology needs to follow standard definitions and terms adoptions from representative organizations ([ISA terms](#), [SAREF](#), [Unit of Measures](#) and [Schema.org](#))

4.2 Implementation language

The selected implementation language for the ontology is OWL, the Ontology Web Language. The serialization format will be performed with the use of the Turtle (TTL) language and JSON-LD serialization to expose the corresponding information and variables acquired and stored in the different data sources as the semantic repository and non-structured databases. Moreover, the selection of SPARQL as semantic query language to retrieve and manipulate the data stored in serialization formats we mentioned in the above section for knowledge graph representation.

¹² <https://isa-specs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/isamodel.html>

4.3 Metadata model & mapping

Based on the deliverable “D1.2.- Semantic model” where describes the ISA framework which offers the most developed and established multi-omics metadata model. In this task we have taken the following ISA schema to describe in a common and standardized way the data retrieved from the different repositories.

Figure 6 ISA metadata model ¹³

This schema, in addition to providing a representation of entities to describe the repositories data, also shows the relationships between them and how they are connected.

The baseline for the knowledge graph construction is to map the data retrieved with its representation inside the schema, so next table shows these relations divided by repositories:

Table 1 Mapping table Repository vs ISA schema

Fields from repositories	ISA Schema data model
Metabolites (Metabolights)	
study	Study.Title
database_identifier	Study.Identifier
chemical_formula	Included in future ontology extension
smiles	Included in future ontology extension
inchi	Included in future ontology extension
metabolite_identification	Included in future ontology extension
taxid	Included in future ontology extension
species	Included in future ontology extension
concentrations	Sample

¹³ <https://isa-specs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/isamodel.html>

Array Express	
title	Study.Title
description	Study.Description
Genomics (GEO repository)	
dataset_name	Study.identifier
dataset_title	Study.title
dataset_description	Study.description
dataset_type	Technology.type
dataset_pubmed_id	Information.identifier.pubmed identifier
dataset_platform	Assay.technology_platform
dataset_platform_technology_type	Assay.technology type
dataset_feature_count	Assay.data
dataset_sample_type	Sample.Type
concentrations	Sample

4.4 Ontology

This section is mainly devoted to the presentation of the GLOMICAVE ISA ontology¹⁴. The work focuses on the description of the concepts represented in the Figure 6 the subsequent implementation in OWL format¹⁵.

Is constructed around a set of key classes and their relationships with on another. Is structured around the concepts of investigation, study, and assay as main classes, which are the backbone of all the ontology, and derived in the definition of subclasses related to them (contact, publications, materials, sources, samples, etc.).

The OWL implementation is defined by the following namespaces:

Table 2 GLOMICAVE ontological prefix

PREFIX	Namespaces
:	https://w3id.org/def/isa-glomicave/
dcterms	http://purl.org/dc/terms/
owl	http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#
rdf	http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#
xsd	http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#
rdfs	http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#
vann	http://purl.org/vocab/vann/
time	http://www.w3.org/2006/time#
sf	http://www.opengis.net/ont/sf#
om	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/
schema	https://schema.org/
saref	https://saref.etsi.org/core/
isaterms	http://purl.org/isaterms
glomicave	https://w3id.org/def/isa-glomicave/

As there is no ontology schematic representation, we used a tool called **Protégé** to provide a quick overview through the figures and shapes and its relations expressed by types of arrows. This tool is able to provide a schematic representation of the ontology based on the OWL implementation. The resulting schema of the ontology looks like Figure 7 which is not a complete representation, but enough to describe its structure:

¹⁴ <https://newt.oerc.ox.ac.uk/isaterms/>

¹⁵ <https://w3id.org/def/isa-glomicave/>

Figure 7 ISA Ontology schema

For the description of the ontology figures and shapes, are used arrows to represent the relationships between classes (object properties). These relationships represent RDF, RDFS, OWL constructs and object properties. Precisely:

Plain arrows between classes indicate a local restriction in the origin class. More frequent restrictions refer to object properties that can be instantiated between the classes in the origin and the destination of the arrow. The identifier of the object property is indicated within the arrow.

Dashed arrows with a white triangle between classes represent the **rdfs:subClassOf** relation between two classes. The origin of the arrow is the class to be declared as a subclass at the destination of the arrow.

4.5 Documentation & publication

The corresponding documentation and version code of the GLOMICAVE ISA ontology can be found the following link:

<https://w3id.org/def/isa-glomicave/>

The documentation of the ontology has been performed by using an external tool called [WIDOCO](#). This tool permits to automatically generate the documentation of the ontology-based on the labels defined in the semantic model. Despite directly using this tool, we preferred to use a continuous integration methodology for ontology documentation and publication. Hence, this procedure will involve once the ontology model is published on GitHub, tests are passed, and the ontology is published using WIDOCO tool. For that purpose, we used [Ontology web tool](#).

Considering this aspect, the main annotations used in the ontology development for documentation purposes are:

Table 3 GLOMICAVE ontology prefix

Annotation	Description
Dc:contributor	Definition of the contributors of the ontology
Dc: creator	Definition of the creators of the ontology
Dc: description	Description of the ontology (indicating main purpose)
Dc:source	Tags of the ontology
Dc:title	Title of the ontology
Dc:created	Date of creation
Dcterms:license	Licence determined for the ontology
Dcterms:modified	Date of the last modification
versionInfo	Version of the ontology
Comment	Description of the main entities and classes
label	Human readable label for the classes and the properties (optional)

After the end of each of the continuous integration processes, we have the ontology published in a custom landing page that could be increased with other ontologies if we work on the same repository. To ensure accessibility, we used a public link and URL under the W3C domain (Figure 8).

isa-glomicave landing page

Here you can find the list of vocabularies that have been found on isa-glomicave.

Ontology	Serialization	License	Language	Description
ISA Abstract Model extended to Metabolites, Gnostic and Metabolomic studies	TURTLE	https://opensource.org/licenses...	en	The proposed ontology not only focused on the abstract reference model but also, served as a extension to different metabolomic, gnostic and metabolites ... See more

Page created with [VocabLite](#) (Ontology Engineering Group)
 Built with [Bootstrap](#)
 Latest revision May, 2022

Figure 8 GLOMICAVE ISA ontology publication

5. Knowledge graph

This section is mainly devoted to explaining the process of the knowledge graph construction, once obtained the data required from all the repositories and stored in a relational database, which at the moment of writing this deliverable was PostgreSQL.

The next step was to transform that data into the structure of the ISA data model and store it in a semantic database. This process was made through Stardog's platform that allows to obtain a dataset queried following the structure defined, in this case the information was retrieved following the ISA data model specified in the following instruction in next figure:


```

1 PREFIX : <http://glomicave.eu/ontology/>
2 MAPPING :MetaboliteMapping
3 FROM SQL {
4   SELECT * FROM public.metabolites
5 }
6 TO {
7   ?metabolite a :Assay ;
8               a :MetabolitesAssay ;
9               :id ?id ;
10              :hasPart ?study ;
11              :databaseid ?database_identifier ;
12              :formula ?chemical_formula .
13 }
14 WHERE {
15   BIND(template("http://glomicave.eu/ontology/Metabolite{id}") AS ?metabolite)
16 }
  
```

Figure 9 Stardog platform: Code to semantic data transformation

The process described previously is known as mapping process, and basically consists in matching the relational database information into the semantic structure to be able to load it in a virtual knowledge graph.

In order to retrieve all the semantic information, it has been necessary to query it through SPARQL commands as depicted in the following Figure 10:


```

1 PREFIX : <http://glomicave.eu/ontology/>
2
3 SELECT *
4 GRAPH <virtual://glomicave> {
5   ?metabolite a :Assay ;
6             a :MetabolitesAssay ;
7             :id ?id ;
8             :hasPart ?study ;
9             :databaseid ?database_identifier ;
10            :formula ?chemical_formula .
11 }
12

```

Figure 10 Stardog platform: SPARQL query

Once obtained the semantic data serialized through triples and stored into NT files, in order to construct the knowledge graph, it is been decided to upload and store such files into TriplyDB, which is a semantic database that allows to integrate data assets into a standard-compliant knowledge graph, and finally permits to publish this graph for its public query and visualization under this link: <https://triplydb.com/aitorcorchero/Glomicave/>

6. Conclusions & Future Work

This last section of the deliverable is mainly devoted to the summary of the conclusions and results (Section 6.1) obtained after the development of the Task 1.3 entitled as “*Knowledge graph construction using integration plug-ins for automated collection*”. This task was finalized with the present deliverable. However, the ontology has to evolve and to be adapted as the project is acquiring data from more repositories, as well as the development of new plug-ins. Accordingly within the objectives of the next packages and their objectives, such as data analytics in the development of WP2, WP3, WP4, visualization in WP5, and elaboration of services and research in different demo-cases in WP6. Hence, any newer requirement refinement and bugs correction that could occur until the end of the project will be reported accordingly.

6.1 Conclusions and Results

The present deliverable has depicted the advancements performed in GLOMICAVE in the:

- Elaboration of a set of plug-ins for automated collection of data from different repositories
- Conversion of data collected under the ISA data model and its ontology
- Store of data retrieved in structured database
- Store data converted in semantic database
- Knowledge graph construction based on data from semantic database

During the elaboration of the plug-ins, it has been necessary to adapt the code devoted to get data from the different sources, as each repository expose the data through different communication protocols. Moreover, extract the relevant data among the large amount of data collected for each investigation, study, assay and values of concentrations it’s been challenging and required the aid of an expert on the domain of multi-omics field.

As one of the big challenges faced during the task, besides the data acquisition was the mapping process between the ISA data model and the data retrieved to provide data under the ISA ontology structure and relationships.

As a conclusion, Task 1.3 establish the bases for a common data model and knowledge exchange in GLOMICAVE.

6.2 Future Work

As mentioned, Task 1.3 has finalized with the present. However, according to the development and progress of the other WPs, we envision as a future task the following actions:

Table 4 GLOMICAVE possible additional actions:

Action	Description
Plug-in's issues	During the process of the data acquisition could appear issues in terms of data conversion or data structure that could cause some unexpected errors, these errors will need to be addressed.
Plug-in's developments	As the project needs to get more data from more repositories, more plug-ins will need to be developed. Moreover, these plug-ins will be part of GLOMICAVE architecture, that implies be exposed as code scripts in Jupyter Notebooks.
Semantic database population	Currently semantic data is stored in TriplyDB but will be stored in Neptune due to project requirements.
Relational database population	Currently storing semantic data in PostgreSQL, but due to the architecture proposed, and accessed through Athena it will be stored in S3 Buckets.
Mapping table update	As the project is advancing and the ISA ontology is extended to represent in detail the data obtained, the "Table 1 Mapping table Repository vs ISA schema" might require some updates.

7. References

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